

OG SAMBUCOSVALOR: A road to elderberry valorisation

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The Forest4Eu project: the Operational Groups

The Horizon Europe Forest4Eu³ Project's fundamental task is to revisit and select relevant information that illustrates the wealth of knowledge and innovation arising from the work of the Operational Groups (OG) in Europe focused on Forestry and Agroforestry themes. The objective is to present this information in different formats to reach a broad audience in the various countries participating in that project. This results in praise of the valuable contribution of many OGs to solving problems linked to the aforementioned sectors and where innovation, as a rule, is present, be it of a technological, organisational or other nature.

Based on the high number of Operational Groups accessed within the scope of Forest4Eu, there was a need to select those associated with themes that were considered most relevant, according to the grid inspired by the current methodology in the EIP Agri /EU Cap Network. The process took place in three fundamental phases: i) Selection and voting by the Project partners through an exhaustive exchange of information, which sought to capture different national sensitivities and interests; ii) Voting carried out by several individuals with recognised competence in the forestry and agroforestry fields; iii) Work sessions, in each of the countries represented in the Project, in which, in addition to the national partners, various specialists were involved, related to political power, consultancy, associations, academia, among others. In these sessions, it was possible to reach a consensus on the OGs and themes considered most relevant for each country and region. In the vote, one that deserved special mention was OG SambucusValor, where elderberry plays a central role. The main reason was that a traditionally cultivated but somewhat neglected plant could have a relevant role in the regional economy of

different European countries. This shrub (or small tree) can be found in several countries in Central Europe and the Iberian Peninsula, presenting a variable productivity according to the bioclimatic region. Traditionally, it has had some symbolism and diverse uses associated with it, although its commercial value seems less significant than its potential makes us believe. In Portugal, the production of fresh berries has been decreasing (possibly due to climate change and the ageing of the population linked to this crop), presenting an annual average in the last four years of 730 tons, according to information provided by RegieFrutas. In the past⁴, it would have reached a fresh berry production of around 2000 tonnes, to which would be added 400 tonnes of dehydrated berries (currently it will be around 20 tonnes, with reduced demand, according to Regiefrutas). It was not possible to measure the current production of fresh flowers. Elderberries, however, have considerable growth potential and can expand to most of the territory in the Central and Northern zones of the country. The reality will be similar in other European countries, but in-depth studies are necessary to support future developments. Interest in this shrub is growing, which could positively affect several action levels.

Methodology

This article was based on manuscripts and results found on the internet concerning OG SambucusValor. No additional substantive material emerged from the Operational Group for the writing presented here. The RegieFrutas cooperative contributed with a critical view on the subject and data on current elderberry production and prospects.

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² RegieFrutas-Dálvares (Tarouca) collaborated on this article and contributed to updating the information. We thank their representative.

³ www.forest4eu.eu. Horizon Europe, Grant Agreement nº. 101086216.

⁴ <https://florestas.pt/conhecer/sabugueiro-um-arbusto-nativo-uma-cultura-com-potencial/>

SambucusValor Operational Group: Description, promoters and chronology

The OG “SambucusValor- Integrated valorisation of elderberries based on healthy consumption patterns: from the plant to the creation of new value-added food products” was financed by PDR2020. The main objective of the established partnership was to contribute to the integrated valorisation of Elderberry as an endogenous resource based on the creation of quality indicators and sustainable production and transformation strategies, which should lead to the emergence of an Elderberry pilot centre to enhance this development, using the resources available from each project partner (public and private)⁵. It took place between 2018 and 2021, in a collaboration between Inovterra- Association for Local Development, Publindustria - Produção de Comunicação Ltda.; Inovfood, Unipessoal Ltda.; National Institute of Agricultural and Veterinary Research; University of Aveiro; José Pedro da Silva Tavares and Alberto Luís Branco Miranda de Carvalho Neto. The fieldwork's territorial base comprised three Douro Sul/Beira Interior Norte region pilots. The objectives of this OG were relatively ambitious, considering the state of neglect of this typical shrub without exploring its full potential, such as berries, flowers, or wood. Its cultivation has been mostly marginal compared to other aspects and activities of the farms where it is located (for example, just being used as a border for fields or being kept in poorer soils without special care). Therefore, technological or management innovation is relevant and can be extrapolated to regions where elderberries can be better monetised.

At OG SambucusValor the main objectives were: i) Definition of flower and berry quality indicators (physical-chemical parameters), which relate the cultivation conditions with the composition of the flower and berry; ii) Implementation of flower and berry stabilisation and storage processes to preserve their bioactive components; iii) Design and development of new food products, namely

freeze-dried products, powders with different particle sizes, concentrates, and dry pressed products, taking advantage of the distinct characteristics of the elderberry flower and berry; iv) Nutritional assessment of the products to be developed; v) Creation of a website, information dissemination networks and partnership network with consumer associations, food companies and elderberry producers; vi) Creation of a pilot elderberry centre.

Results of OG SambucusValor: summary

Elderberry (*Sambucus nigra*) belongs to the *Sambucus* genus - Adoxaceae family. It is a shrub that grows four to five meters in height but can reach much more if properly cultivated. Deciduous, the crown is dense and rounded, supported by an irregular trunk and numerous flexible branches, covered by a rough, greyish bark. The inside of the branches (pith) is white and spongy. The varieties identified as being the most important are ‘Elderberry’, generally characterised by having clusters and small, although heavy, berries; ‘Sabugueira’, which produces large bunches with equally large berries; and ‘Bastardeira’, with characteristics of the other two varieties. It is a pioneer species with more lavish adaptation to cool and humid areas.

Elderberry berries (or drupes) are spherical, about seven millimetres in diameter. They ripen between August and September, acquiring a very dark purple or purplish hue, which signals their maturity. This berry colour is very typical in Portugal, distinguishing and valuing it compared to berries produced in other countries. Both flowers and fruits are found grouped in clusters or pendulous infructescence.

⁵ <https://inovacao.rederural.gov.pt/2/122-valorizacao-integrada-do-sabugueiro-em-funcao-dos-padroes-de-consumo-saudavel-da-planta-a-criacao-de-novos-produtos-alimentares-de-valor-acrescentado>

The results of OG SambucusValor can be summarised as follows⁶:

a) Determination of flower and berry quality indicators:

Berry samples were collected between 2018 and 2021, verifying that pH and total soluble solids values increase throughout ripening, ranging from 3.43 to 5.02 and 5.0 to 20.4 °Brix, respectively. It was found that elderberries from Portuguese cultivars have a higher SST content (total soluble solids content, an indicator of soluble sugar content) than that reported for other European cultivars. These differences can be explained by the specific edaphoclimatic conditions of mainland Portugal, with higher average temperatures than those occurring in Central Europe and presenting a more significant number of hours of daily sun exposure. Comparisons were made between the varieties of this species (reported previously), revealing that 'Sabugueira' has higher SST content. Total phenolic content and antioxidant activity increase during maturation in all experimental fields, cultivars, and harvest years. The climatic year is the main factor that influences the quality of the berry; on the other hand, years with more significant rainfall and water availability are essential for obtaining berries with higher quality parameters.

b) Analysis of cyanogenic compounds present in elderberry:

Given the interest aroused by elderberry, it is necessary to check the possible presence of cyanogenic compounds that are potentially toxic to humans and important in food safety. The methodology followed in OG sought to evaluate the content of those berries collected in the final maturation stage according to the following process: crushing, extraction, centrifugation and filtering. The results demonstrate the relatively low toxicity of the berries, as the levels of cyanogenic compounds vary from 10 to 133 µg of sambunigrin/g of dry weight of berry. The 'Sabugueiro' variety was the one with the lowest value. According to the

European Medicines Agency [Committee on Herbal Medicinal Products Assessment report on *Sambucus nigra* L., fructus. Eur. Med. Agency 2013, 44, 1–26.] toxicity limits for sambunigrin are approximately 330 µg/g berry weight. The results obtained under the OG align with those previously reported by the European Medicines Agency, which indicates that the consumption of ripe berries does not raise toxicity problems for humans.

c) Creation of a web platform and dissemination networks:

The creation of the website www.sambucusvalor.pt was considered very relevant as a basis for interaction between agents and organisations interested in Sabugueiro. Various types of initiatives were initiated for its dissemination and dissemination, such as participating in technical fairs across the country, business networks (Hungary and Romania), international meetings to promote elderberry cultivation and fostering networks of contacts identified as essential for the completion of the OG work; publications in global and national scientific journals; organisation of work sessions aimed at this culture, among others. Inovterra (one of OG's partners) made promotional videos for OG SambucusValor, such as <https://youtu.be/17Ep-wlLw3o> (about pruning bushes), <https://youtu.be/SdjiiO15zKs> (about harvesting the flower and fruit) and <https://youtu.be/ZZAOQxeEazs> (about laboratory research, under the responsibility of the University of Aveiro). However, it should be noted that the website is not active, but promotional videos and some technical documentation are available.

As a final note in this Point III, it should be noted that the results presented, especially in paragraphs a) and b), are partially similar to those obtained in a study⁷ contemporary to OG on elderberry, particularly concerning the physicochemical characterisation of elderberry, the varieties and the differentiation between them.

⁶ <https://inovacao.rederural.gov.pt/2/122-valorizacao-integrada-do-sabugueiro-em-funcao-dos-padroes-de-consumo-saudavel-da-planta-a-criacao-de-novos-produtos-alimentares-de-valor-acrescentado> : Final Conclusions of OG Sambucus Valor (pdf)

⁷ Project "BagaConValor – Criação de valor no processo tecnológico de produção de sumo concentrado de baga de sabugueiro", financed by Programa Operacional Temático Competitividade e Internacionalização proposed by Indumape, on behalf a partnership with RegieFrutas, Universidade de Trás-os-Montes and Instituto Politécnico de Viseu. It lasted from 2018-2021. <https://www.cesam-la.pt/projetos/bagaconvalor-criacao-de-valor-no-processo-tecnologico-de>

Scientific and productive interest associated with Elderberry: some examples

Researchers and producers are centrally concerned about creating new by-products and partnering with partners to promote elderberries' diversified profitability. More than exporting the berry, they seek to create value through its transformation.

Already, national and international partnerships pave the way for new ways of consuming elderberries (jellies, sweets, among others). Cooperation with entities in Galicia has already allowed mutual enrichment and collaboration in research and practice. The University of Aveiro has given particular emphasis to this crop in the search for food security, innovation, and alternative uses that can take advantage of market niches - an example is the use of the residue (pomace) resulting from the preparation of the berries, extracting a powder which can be added to yoghurts, porridge, water, or which can be integrated into the preparation of desserts and bakery products, among others ⁸. Juice and powder are appreciable sources of carbohydrates, calcium, and magnesium, and they have a low amount of lipids, making them low-energy foods. It is concluded that the flower and berry can be explored as raw material sources for developing value-added food products. The University of Trás-os-Montes has also supported elderberry cultivation, covering various aspects of its production and maintenance as a bush, allowing it to extend its useful life and reduce variability in the quantity and quality of the products.

Elderberry is a good example of how a well-known but neglected plant can mitigate the adverse effects of an unbalanced and little-variety diet. Given its adaptation to many European regions, it has the potential to improve health and quality of life, ecological diversity, and environmental sustainability within the vivification of the regional economy. In all these examples, cooperation between producers, their representatives, industry, regional political

power and scientific research has been notable. Furthermore, a concern has been about cyclically promoting debates and demonstrations related to different aspects of this culture and its respective use.

The Elderberry producer's point of view: investments, profitability, uses of the plant and entrepreneurship

From the documentary consultations and the opinion of RegieFrutas, aspects worth highlighting stand out. As a starting point, it seems unanimous that elderberry cultivation can play a critical role in rural reorganisation and the interface with forest areas and can also contribute to stimulating the use of abandoned or unattractive fields for investment. These factors may be associated with increased biodiversity and mitigating the effects of climate change and fire management. Therefore, support for elderberry-related investment should pay attention to aspects proven to be important in this activity. Irrigation to improve productivity, good drainage and adequate fertilisation can be interesting investments for elderberry orchards, as their productivity increases by around 30%. (according to the tests carried out). Pests and diseases also deserve increasing attention, especially in orderly plantings with an expanded market as their primary objective.

In recent years, necessary steps have been taken with public bodies to implement support for the planting of elderberries. These are expected to be made available soon, bringing a new dynamic to this culture, which, in the opinion of those contacted, still needs to be improved.

The implementation of the market and the exploration of high-value-added products have a long way to go. Two complementary aspects seem especially relevant:

1. Research focusing on the cultivation of bushes, the choice of varieties, and planting, leading to the assumption of elderberry as a non-marginal crop conducted rationally and

sustainably. The approach to the possible mechanisation of fruit harvesting is also relevant, as is the promotion of plantations and the attraction of young entrepreneurs to this crop. It involves conquering areas of other less profitable crops or promoting their implementation in less favoured regions from the point of view of soil and climate conditions;

2. Monetize and diversify the uses of the plant, promoting it to consumers. In Portugal, elderflower is very little consumed, and most elderberry production is directed towards obtaining berries, mainly exported to northern Europe (although the national market shows a growing trend in consumption of the must);

Elderberry consumption still needs to be rooted in national eating habits, highlighting the need to explore the market, especially in northern Europe, which has a more excellent tradition of consuming wild fruits. The necessary increase in producer prices to make the crop attractive could come in this way. The Brix, patented by berries produced in Portugal, is a positive differentiating aspect of their commercial value and can be valued. However, even though the Brix is not the same in all municipalities (the region of excellence is made up of the municipalities of Tarouca, Lamego, Armamar, Tabuaço and Moimenta da Beira), the current market already accepts and values berries from neighbouring regions. This aspect is fundamental for expanding the area cultivated with this shrub. To reflect on the market associated with this shrub, it is necessary to consider that the elderberry has a useful life of around 35 years, with around 20 years of full production: this happens from the third year in which the first berries and two more are needed to reach full yield. A good elderberry productivity could vary between 8 and 12 kilos of berries per tree⁹; however, less rainfall and high temperatures have not allowed this value to be reached in recent years. In Portugal, the average value of a kilogram of fresh berries is 50 cents, that of dehydrated berries is 3 euros (to obtain 1 kg of dehydrated berries, you need at least 6 kg

of fresh berries), and that of flowers is 5. 50 euros.

The RegieFrutas cooperative

From 2005 onwards, the market focused on the search for fresh products, a fundamental reason for creating the Regiefrutas (Tarouca) cooperative, which has all the inherent technological and scientific processes and the capacity to meet food safety demands.

It began operating in 2009 and has equipment to transform and freeze fruits, giving an essential boost to the penetration of elderberries in the market and eliminating the almost mandatory need to dehydrate the berries for later sale. The must produced at Regiefrutas has been ISO 22000 accredited since 2011.

The manufacturing unit concentrates and directs production, meaning that its management can be done on a less case-by-case basis. Most berries (Individually Quick Frozen-IQF) go to the European market. The installed processing capacity (3,500 tons are produced during the berry harvest period, which takes place for approximately 5 to 6 weeks in the summer) allows, however, a significant increase that may occur in production. It is worth mentioning that Regiefrutas is the only company nationwide capable of this process, and the installed capacity versus current production covers the needs of producers and buyers. Furthermore, the existing equipment supports other regional fruit productions in a logic of profitability (working all year round and avoiding seasonal peaks) and diversification.

⁹ <https://florestas.pt/conhecer/sabugueiro-um-arbusto-nativo-uma-cultura-com-potencial/>

Final note:

Despite some fluctuations and the population ageing linked to elderberry production (mainly on tiny farms), there has been a growth trend. New plantations are promoted by young farmers, where irrigation and soil deserve particular attention to improve and stabilise elderberry productivity. An important aspect is the cuttings certification; here, the work with nurseries deserves specific attention.

Innovation, technology, food security, the factory structure, adequate financial support and the rational management of orchards can increase the already renewed interest in this production.

Further information

<https://florestas.pt/conhecer/sabugueiro-um-arbusto-nativo-uma-cultura-com-potencial/>
https://jb.utad.pt/especie/Sambucus_nigra_subesp_nigra

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